

Convenient synthesis of 1-*N*,7-*N*-bisethoxyphthalimido-4-(3,5-dimethyl-4-substitutedphenyl)-4,7-dihydro-1*H*-dipyrazolo[3,4-*b*;4',3'-*e*]pyridin-8-yl)-phenylamine

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Abstract : In the three component one pot synthesis 5-methyl-2,4-dihydro-3*H*-pyrazole-3-one reacted with substituted aldehydes and *p*-phenylenediamine to produce 4-{3,5-dimethyl-4-(substitutedphenyl)-4,7-dihydro-1*H*-dipyrazolo[3,4-*b*;4',3'-*e*]pyridin-8-yl}phenylamine (4a-e). Condensation of (4a-e) with two mole of bromoethoxyphthalimide in ethanol using pyridine as a base afforded 1-*N*,7-*N*-bisethoxyphthalimido-4-(3,5-dimethyl-4-substitutedphenyl)-4,7-dipyrazolo[3,4-*b*;4',3'-*e*]pyridine-8-yl)-phenylamine (5a-e). Structure of the synthesized compounds were confirmed on the basis of elemental analyses and spectral studies.

Keywords : Substituted aldehydes, bromoethoxyphthalimide, pyridine.

Introduction

Heterocyclic compounds represent an important class of biologically active molecules. Specifically, those containing the pyrazole nucleus have been shown to possess various biological activities¹ as herbicides, fungicides, analgesics, etc. The pyrazole unit is one of the core structure in a number of natural products. Many pyrazole derivatives are known to exhibit a wide range of biological properties such as analgesic, antipyretic, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetics²⁻⁴, insecticidal, matricidal and hypoglycemic activities⁵⁻⁷ of pyrazole have been reported. Pinto⁸ has reported medicinal importance of pyrazole derivatives. Incorporation of heterocyclic rings into prospective pharmaceutical candidates is a major tactic to gain activity and safety advantages. Much work has been directed toward the design and synthesis of fused-pyrazole derivatives⁹⁻¹⁴. Substituted 1,4-dihydropyridines (1,4-DHPs) are well known as Ca²⁺ channel blockers and emerged as one of the most important classes of drugs for the treatment of cardiovascular diseases including hypertension¹⁵. 1,4-Dihydropyridines possess a variety of biological activities such as, vasodilator, bronchodilator, anti-atherosclerotic, antitumor, geroprotective, hepatoprotective and antidiabetic agent^{16,17}. Recent studies have revealed that 1,4-DHPs exhibit several medicinal appli-

cations which include neuroprotectant¹⁸ and platelet anti-aggregatory activity¹⁹, into addition cerebral antiischemic activity in the treatment of Alzheimer's disease²⁰ and as chemosensitizer in tumor therapy²¹. These examples clearly demonstrate the remarkable potential of DHP derivatives as a source of valuable drug candidates. Various combination of heterocyclic rings attached to alkoxyphthalimide group have been synthesized²³ and tested for antimicrobial²⁴ and antimalarial²⁵ activities.

Results and discussion

An attempt has been made to undertake the synthesis of ethoxyphthalimide derivatives of some dipyrazolopyridine through a three component one pot synthetic process. 4-{3,5-Dimethyl-4-(substitutedphenyl)-4,7-dihydro-1*H*-dipyrazolo[3,4-*b*;4',3'-*e*]pyridin-8-yl)-phenylamine (4a-e) were prepared by one pot three components reaction of 5-methyl-2,4-dihydro-3*H*-pyrazole-3-one, with substituted aldehydes and *p*-phenylenediamine using ethanol as a solvent. Formation of the product (4a) was confirmed by a sharp peak at 3320-3355 for NH₂ and 3230 cm⁻¹ for NH group along in IR spectra. Treatment of (4a-e) with two mole of bromoethoxyphthalimide using pyridine as a base afforded 1-*N*,7-*N*-bisethoxyphthalimido-4-(3,5-dimethyl-4-substituted-phenyl)-4,7-dihydro-1*H*-dipyrazolo[3,4-*b*;4',3'-*e*]pyridine-8-yl)-phenylamine

Reaction Scheme

(5a-e). Formation of (5a) was confirmed by appearance of two triplets at δ 4.2 (t, O-CH₂) and 3.5 (t, N-CH₂) in the ¹H NMR spectra and disappearance of a singlet at 8.26 (NH of pyrazole ring,) indicated that the reaction at the ring NH.

Experimental

General :

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and

are therefore uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked on silica gel G TLC plates of 2 mm thickness using n-hexane and ethyl acetate as solvent system. The visualization of spot was carried out in an iodine chamber. The IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrometer. The ¹H NMR spectra were scanned on a Bruker DRX-300 MHz spectrometer (300 MHz) in (DMSO-d₆) using TMS as internal standard and chemical shifts are expressed in δ ppm. The mass spectra were recorded

on a Joel SX-102 (FAB) spectrometer. Phthalimidoxyethyl bromide was synthesized by the reported method²² and 5-methyl-2,4-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one (1) as synthesized by literature method.

Synthesis of 4-{3,5-dimethyl-4-(phenyl)-4,7-dihydro-1H-dipyrzolo[3,4-b;4',3'-e]pyridin-8-yl}-phenylamine (4a) :

A mixture of 5-methyl-2,4-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one (0.02 mol), benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) and *p*-phenylenediamine (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was heated under reflux for 7 h. The mixture was cooled and the separated solid was filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 160 °C.

Similarly, compounds **4b-e** were also synthesized by minor change in reflux times. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3320–3355 (NH₂ str.), 3230 (N-H str.), 3075 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1610 (C=N str.), 1228 (C-N); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 8.26 (s, NH), 3.6 (s, NH₂), 6.90–7.80 (9H, m, Ar-H), 2.49 (s, CH₃), 5.21 (s, CH); ¹³C NMR δ : 12.8, 102.5, 116.7, 120.6, 124.9, 128.4, 129.4, 134.8, 137.7, 138.5, 139.5, 139.2, 152.7; m.p. 172 °C; mol. formula C₂₁H₂₀N₆; Analysis of N% Calcd. 21.58, Found 23.78.

4-{3,5-Dimethyl-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-4,7-dihydro-1H-dipyrzolo[3,4-b;4',3'-e]pyridin-8-yl}-phenylamine (4b) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3348–3365 (NH₂ str.), 3239 (N-H str.), 3080 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1615 (C=N str.), 1233 (C-N), 735 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 8.34 (s, NH), 3.9 (s, NH₂), 6.95–8.10 (m, Ar-H), 2.61 (s, CH₃), 5.28 (s, CH); ¹³C NMR δ : 12.8, 103.5, 116.7, 119.0, 128.4, 131.7, 133.5, 135.3, 135.7, 137.0, 139.4, 143.6, 153.5; m.p. 168 °C; mol. formula C₂₁H₁₉ClN₆; Analysis of N% Calcd. 21.50, Found 23.79.

4-{3,5-Dimethyl-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-4,7-dihydro-1H-dipyrzolo[3,4-b;4',3'-e]pyridin-8-yl}-phenylamine (4c) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3350–3373 (NH₂ str.), 3243 (N-H str.), 3093 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1618 (C=N str.), NO₂ (1553–1339), 1237 (C-N); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 8.46 (s, NH), 4.0 (s, NH₂), 7.10–8.16 (m, Ar-H), 2.63 (s, CH₃), 5.31 (1H, s, CH); ¹³C NMR δ : 12.8, 104.5, 118.9, 119.5, 120.0, 124.6, 129.1, 133.5, 135.5, 135.9, 138.3, 139.7, 140.2, 147.0, 155.8; m.p. 168 °C; mol. formula C₂₁H₁₉N₂O₂; Analysis of N% Calcd. 24.42, Found 24.15.

4-{3,5-Dimethyl-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4,7-dihydro-1H-dipyrzolo[3,4-b;4',3'-e]pyridin-8-yl}-phenylamine (4d) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3346–3369 (NH₂ str.), 3237 (N-H str.), 3089 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1612 (C=N str.), 1228 (C-N), 1208 (C-O-C); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 8.40 (s,

NH), 3.8 (s, NH₂), 7.26–8.20 (m, Ar-H), 2.60 (s, CH₃), 5.27 (s, CH), 3.12 (O-CH₃); ¹³C NMR δ : 12.8, 57.2, 103.4, 114.6, 117.8, 119.0, 130.4, 134.5, 136.8, 137.8, 139.5, 140.4, 154.6, 158.7; m.p. 177 °C; mol. formula C₂₂H₂₂N₆O; Analysis of N% Calcd. 21.75, Found 21.89.

4-{3,5-Dimethyl-4-(4-N,N-dimethylamino)-4,7-dihydro-1H-dipyrzolo[3,4-b;4',3'-e]pyridin-8-yl}-phenylamine (4e) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3341–3367 (NH₂ str.), 3235 (N-H str.), 3082 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1612 (C=N str.), 1236 (C-N); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 8.41 (s, NH), 3.6 (s, NH₂), 6.92–8.15 (m, Ar-H), 2.54 (s, CH₃), 5.26 (s, CH); ¹³C NMR δ : 12.8, 42.5, 103.5, 115.3, 116.7, 119.3, 126.4, 130.5, 134.2, 137.6, 137.9, 138.5, 143.5, 155.9; m.p. 163 °C; mol. formula C₂₃H₂₅N₇; Analysis of N% Calcd. 24.54, Found 24.39.

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To a solution of **4a** (0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol were added phthalimidoxyethylbromide (0.02 mol) and pyridine (0.02 mol). The mixture was heated at refluxed for 9 h. It was filtered and poured into crushed ice. The solid thus separated, was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol to yield needle shaped shining white crystals.

Other derivative **5(b-e)** were also prepared by similar method.

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3358–3369 (NH₂ str.), 1732 (C=O), 1618 (C=N str.), 1231 (C-N); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 4.0 (s, NH₂), 6.85–7.51 (m, Ar-H), 2.50 (s, CH₃), 5.21 (s, CH), 4.2 (t, O-CH₂), 3.5 (t, N-CH₂); ¹³C NMR δ : 14.5, 49.2, 68.3, 103.7, 116.7, 117.3, 124.6, 127.4, 128.0, 128.5, 131.6, 133.4, 135.6, 136.3, 138.2, 138.9, 144.8, 155.3, 162.7; m.p. 192 °C; mol. formula C₄₁H₃₄N₈O₆; Analysis of N% Calcd. 15.25, Found 15.08.

1-N,7-N-Bisethoxyphthalimido-4-{3,5-dimethyl-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-4,7-dihydro-1H-dipyrzolo[3,4-b;4',3'-e]pyridin-8-yl}-phenylamine (5b) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3363–3382 (NH₂ str.), 1739 (C=O), 1621 (C=N str.), 1234 (C-N), 741 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 4.3 (s, NH₂), 6.93–7.98 (m, Ar-H), 2.73 (s, CH₃), 5.26 (s, CH), 4.4 (t, O-CH₂), 3.7 (t, N-CH₂); ¹³C NMR δ : 14.5, 47.5, 68.9, 102.4, 118.4, 118.9, 128.5, 129.5, 131.0, 132.4, 133.6, 135.2, 135.8, 136.7, 136.9, 139.1, 144.0, 155.3, 162.7; m.p. 205 °C; mol. formula C₄₁H₃₃ClN₈O₆; Analysis of N % Calcd. 14.57, Found 14.81.

1-N,7-N-Bisethoxyphthalimido-4-{3,5-dimethyl-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-4,7-dihydro-1H-dipyrzolo[3,4-b;4',3'-e]pyridin-8-yl}-phenylamine (5c) :

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3365–3387 (NH_2 str.), 1743 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1625 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$ str.), 1236 ($\text{C}-\text{N}$), 1351–1654 (NO_2); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ : 4.5 (s, NH_2), 6.97–8.10 (m, Ar-H), 2.79 (s, CH_3), 5.33 (s, CH), 4.7 (t, $\text{O}-\text{CH}_2$), 3.9 (t, $\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$); ^{13}C NMR δ : 14.6, 49.2, 69.3, 103.6, 117.4, 118.4, 119.0, 124.5, 127.5, 129.8, 131.5, 132.6, 133.0, 135.4, 136.3, 137.1, 138.4, 139.6, 148.3, 153.8, 162.9; m.p. 199 °C; mol. formula $\text{C}_{41}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_9\text{O}_8$; Analysis of N% Calcd. 16.17, Found 16.28.

1-N,7-N-Bisethoxyphthalimido-4-{3,5-dimethyl-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4,7-dihydro-1H-dipyrzolo[3,4-b;4',3'-e]pyridin-8-yl}-phenylamine (5d) :

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3364–3379 (NH_2 str.), 1735 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1619 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$ str.), 1231 ($\text{C}-\text{N}$); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ : 4.1 (s, NH_2), 6.91–7.95 (m, Ar-H), 2.71 (s, CH_3), 5.21 (s, CH), 4.2 (t, $\text{O}-\text{CH}_2$), 3.1 (t, $\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$), 3.31 (s, OCH_3); ^{13}C NMR δ : 14.5, 49.4, 56.3, 68.3, 103.5, 117.5, 118.4, 127.3, 128.7, 131.0, 132.5, 132.5, 135.6, 136.7, 137.8, 138.3, 138.9, 139.0, 153.6, 162.6; m.p. 201 °C; mol. formula $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_8\text{O}_7$; Analysis of N% Calcd. 14.65, Found 14.82.

1-N,7-N-Bisethoxyphthalimido-4-{3,5-dimethyl-4-(4-N,N-dimethylaminophenyl)-4,7-dihydro-1H-dipyrzolo[3,4-b;4',3'-e]pyridin-8-yl}-phenylamine (5e) :

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3360–3376 (NH_2 str.), 1738 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1620 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$ str.), 1228 ($\text{C}-\text{N}$); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ : 4.0 (s, NH_2), 6.93–7.98 (m, Ar-H), 2.70 (s, CH_3), 5.19 (s, CH), 4.2 (t, $\text{O}-\text{CH}_2$), 3.3 (t, $\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$), 3.69 ($\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$); ^{13}C NMR δ : 14.5, 42.6, 48.6, 68.0, 103.5, 117.5, 118.3, 126.8, 127.9, 128.2, 132.6, 132.7, 132.9, 136.8, 138.2, 139.6, 144.7, 145.9, 153.0, 161.5; m.p. 194 °C; mol. formula $\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{39}\text{N}_9\text{O}_6$; Analysis of N% Calcd. 16.21, Found 16.52.

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